

ISic1373

I.Sicily inscription 1373

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Paterniano

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140878

1. ἐνθά [δε κεῖται — —]

2. ΞΕΝΑΠΟ [— — — — —]

3. ΚΟΙ [— — — — —]

4. καὶ εἶ τ [ις τολμήσει]

5. ἀνῶξ [αι — — — — —]

6.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492986

EDCS 39101753

PHI 140878

Bibliography

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